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**International Journal of
Advances in Engineering &
Scientific Research (IJAESR)**

ISSN: 2349 –3607 (Online)
ISSN: 2349 –4824 (Print)

Available online at:
<http://www.arseam.com/content/volume-1-issue-5-sep-2014>
Email: editor@arseam.com

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ESTIMATION OF SOIL EROSION USING REVISED UNIVERSAL SOIL LOSS EQUATION FOR HAROHALLI WATERSHED

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Abstract-

Soil erosion is the detachment and transportation of soil materials from one place to another, resulting in the removal of the uppermost fertile soil layer, thus decreasing its productivity. Soil erosion was estimated by using Universal Soil Loss Equation in a GIS environment and prioritization of catchments on that basis, the present study Harohalli watershed, Kanakapura Taluk, Ramanagara District area was chosen since it falls in the rocks and granite area. Soil and slope maps were prepared from Survey of India maps and NBSS & LUP maps and integrated into GIS database. Soil erosion of each of the sub catchment was estimated from the integrated map. The sub catchments were prioritized based on the estimation of erosion. From the study it can be inferred that soil erosion estimation using Remote Sensing and GIS technique can be effectively used for prioritization of catchments and this helps in the way the catchments can be taken for treatment for conservation measures.

Keywords — erosion, GIS, prioritization, remote sensing, USLE

1.

INTRODUCTION

Soil is a precious gift of nature to mankind. Ironically, soil is the most neglected commodity on the earth. Soil erosion is one of the most serious problems for environmentalists, which must be taken into consideration to prevent ecological imbalance in nature, basically among natural resource like soil, water and plants. Soil erosion is the detachment and transportation of soil materials from one place to another,

resulting in the removal of the uppermost fertile soil layer, thus decreasing its productivity (Schwab et al., 2002). Overgrazing, deforestation, faulty cultivation and carelessly build roads in watershed areas, have lead to enormous soil erosion.

Erosion removes organic matter from soil and contributes to breakdown of the soil structure that will in turn affect soil fertility and the crop yields. Soil erosion causes siltation of reservoirs, which ultimately reduces the life of the project and affects generation of hydroelectric power. It also affects the flora and fauna of the earth. Eroded sediment can carry nutrients particularly phosphates to waterways, and contribute to eutrophication of lakes and streams. Adsorbed pesticides carried with eroded sediments, adversely affect surface water quality. Soil conservation is the process by which the soil is checked, reducing the velocity of runoff through erosion control measures for maximum sustained crop production and for protection of human life. Soil conservation not only increases the crop yield but also prevents further deterioration of land. The study and estimation of soil erosion is essential for assessing the health and function of watersheds and eutrophication of their water bodies.

Basically there are two types of soil erosion they are:

- i). Erosion that takes place due to wind and water known as *Geological erosion*.
- ii). Erosion that takes place due to over exploitation of land surface known as *Accelerated erosion*.

II. STUDY AREA

The study area taken is the study Harohalli watershed, Kanakapura Taluk, Ramanagara District area was chosen since it falls in the rocks and granite area. The study area geographically lies between 77° 23' 45" E and 77° 38' 20" E longitude and 12° 38' 55" N and 12° 52' 20" N latitude, The watershed covers an area 281.56 Sq.km and is covered in Survey of India (SOI) Toposheets numbers 57 H/5, 57H/6, 57H/9 and 57 H/10. The maximum length and width of the watershed is approximately equal to 31.65km to 13.35km respectively

III. DATA USED

Satellite Image of IRS-P6 LISS-III (acquired on 2006) and Survey of India toposheets mentioned above of 1:50,000 scale as collateral data.

IV. METHODOLOGY

This study describes the basic concepts, the procedure of the RUSLE model, in addition to the methodology to estimate six parameters, and parameter prediction of the RUSLE model. Based on the rainfall storm events, DEM, soil type map, and land cover map, six parameters of the RUSLE model will be estimated and verified as to the reasonability of the parameter estimation results.

V. SOIL LOSS ESTIMATION BY USLE MODEL

The extent of erosion, specific degradation, and sediment yield from watersheds are related to a complex interaction between topography, geology, climate, soil, vegetation, land use, and man-made developments (Shen and Julien, 1993). The USLE is the method most widely used around the world to predict long-term rates of intrill and rill erosion from field or farm size units subject to different management practices. Wischmeier and Smith (1965) developed the USLE based on many years of data from about 10,000 small test plots throughout the U.S. Each test plot had about 22m flow lengths and they were all operated in a similar manner, allowing the soil loss measurements to be combined into a predictive tool. RUSLE was developed to incorporate new research since the earlier USLE publication in 1978 (Wischmeier and Smith, 1978). Agriculture Handbook 703 (Renard et al., 1997) is a guide to conservation planning with the RUSLE.

The underlying assumption in the RUSLE is that detachment and deposition are controlled by the sediment content of the flow. The erosion material is not source limited, but the erosion is limited by the

carrying capacity of the flow. When the sediment load reaches the carrying capacity of the flow, detachment can no longer occur. Sedimentation must also occur during the receding portion of the hydrograph as the flow rate decreases. The basic form of the RUSLE equation has remained the same, but modifications in several of the factors have changed. Both USLE and RUSLE compute the average annual erosion expected on field slopes and are shown in equation 1.0

$$A = R. K. L. S. C. P \quad (1.0)$$

where,

- A = computed spatial average soil loss and temporal average soil loss per unit of area, expressed in the units selected for K and for the period selected for R. In practice, these are usually selected so that A is expressed in $\text{ton} \times \text{acre}^{-1} \times \text{yr}^{-1}$, but other units can be selected (that is, $\text{ton} \times \text{ha}^{-1} \times \text{yr}^{-1}$);
- R = rainfall-runoff erosivity factor—the rainfall erosion index plus a factor for any significant runoff from snowmelt ($100\text{ft} \times \text{tonf} \times \text{acre}^{-1} \times \text{yr}^{-1}$);
- K = soil erodibility factor – the soil-loss rate per erosion index unit for a specified soil as measured on a standard plot, which is defined as a 72.6-ft (22.1- m) length of uniform 9% slope in continuous clean-tilled fallow;
- L = slope length factor – the ratio of soil loss from the field slope length to soil loss from a 72.6-ft length under identical conditions;
- S = slope steepness factor – the ratio of soil loss from the field slope gradient to soil loss from a 9% slope under otherwise identical conditions.
- C = cover management factor – the ratio of soil loss from an area with specified cover and management to soil loss from an identical area in tilled continuous fallow.
- P = support practice factor – the ratio of soil loss with a support practice like contouring, strip cropping, or terracing to soil loss with straight-row farming up and down the slope.

The magnitude of soil erosion depends on two forces—the detachment of soil particles by the impact of rainfall energy called the erosivity of rain, and the ability of the soil to resist the detachment of its particles by this force called the erodibility of soil. This relation is expressed as shown below

$$\text{Soil erosion} = f [(erosivity \text{ of rain}) \times (erodibility \text{ of soil})] \quad (1.2)$$

The RUSLE is also based on similar principles. The erosivity of rain is represented by the factor R and the erodibility of soil surface system by the multiples of the factors KLSCP. In systems terminology considering the watershed as a system represented by the multiples of the factors KLSCP, the input force is represented by the rainfall erosivity factor R and the output (the response to the input), which is the soil erosion is represented by the letter A

VI. RAINFALL EROSIVITY FACTOR (R)

The rainfall erosivity factor is a function of falling raindrops and the rainfall intensity. Wischmeier and Smith (1958) found that the product of kinetic energy of the raindrop and the maximum intensity of rainfall over duration of 30 minutes, in a storm, is the best estimator of soil loss. This product is known as the Erosion Index (EI) value. For a given storm the EI value is determined by multiplying the kinetic energy of the storm to the maximum 30-minute for that storm. The EI values for all the storms occurring in a given year for location are added to obtain an annual erosivity index. The EI_{30} can be expressed as follows:

$$EI_{30} = \frac{(KE)I_{30}}{100} \quad (1.3)$$

Where,

EI_{30} = Erosion index

KE = Kinetic energy of storm

I_{30} = Maximum 30 minute rainfall intensity of the storm

Kinetic energy can be expressed as:

$$KE = 210.3 + 89 \log_{10} I \quad (1.4)$$

Where,

KE = Kinetic energy in ton/ha-cm

I = Rainfall intensity in cm/hr

Wischmeier and Smith (1965) found that the best predictor of rainfall erosivity factor (R) was:

$$R = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \left[\sum_{k=1}^m (E)(I_{30})_k \right] \quad (1.5)$$

where:

R = rainfall-runoff erosivity factor—the rainfall erosion index plus a factor for any significant runoff from snowmelt (100ft×tonf×acre-1×yr-1);

E = the total storm kinetic energy in hundreds of ft-tons per acre;

I₃₀ = the maximum 30-minute rainfall intensity;

j= the counter for each year used to produce the average;

k= the counter for the number of storms in a year;

m= the number of storms n each year;

n= the number of years used to obtain the average R.

The rainfall factor (R) for the present study has been taken from published Isopleth Map of India (Raghunath et al., 1982). This map has prepared, based on 50 years of weather cycles, provides information on erosive forces of rainfall. For the present study, rainfall factor was taken directly as 250 from the Isopleth Map of India. Fig. 1.1 shows the Isopleth Map of India

VII. SOIL ERODIBILITY FACTOR (K)

The soil erodibility factor K is a measure of standard plot 22.1m long, on a 9% slope maintained in a continuous fallow, tilled up and down hill periodically to control weeds and break crust that are formed on the soil surface. The soil erodibility factor (K) relates the rate at which different soils erode under the conditions of equal slope, rainfall. Some soils erode more easily than others due to inherent soil characteristics such as texture, structure, permeability and organic matter content.

The soil erodibility factor (K) calculated from the following equation (Wischmeier and Smith, 1978)

$$100K = 2.1 \times 10^{-4} (N_1 \cdot N_2)^{1.14} (12 - OM) + 3.25(S-2) + 2.5(P-3) \quad (1.6)$$

Where,

K = Soil erodibility factor.

N₁, N₂ = Particle size parameter (% silt + % very fined sand).

OM = Percent organic matter content.

S = Soil structure code (very fine granular = 1; fine granular = 2; medium or coarse granular = 3; blocky, platy, or massive = 4).

P = profile permeability class (rapid = 1; moderate to rapid = 2; moderate = 3; slow to moderate = 4; slow = 5; very slow =6).

The particle size distribution of soils to evaluate 'K' values uses the grain size as (0.1-2.0) mm for sand, (0.05-0.10) mm for very fine sand and (0.002-0.05) mm for silt. In order to use the above Wischmeier's equation, it is necessary that the grain size of the soils in the watershed area brought down to above sizes. This can be obtained by plotting cumulative percentage of silt, very fine sand and coarse sand along log scale versus percentage finer. The soil in the watershed consists of coarse (medium) granular, blocky platy or massive type of soil structure for the calculation of K factor. The soil erodibility factor K for different soils in the watershed is shown in Table 1.1. The K-factor estimated for all the watersheds in the watershed is shown in Table 1.2.

Union of soil map and watershed map were used to identify the different soil types constituting in each watershed. Majority of the watersheds comprises more than one type of soil series. Therefore, dominant soil series in watershed has been taken for calculating the 'K' factor values. If the percentage of sand is more, then there will be voids between the particles and hence it will allow the water to pass through the voids. From this, it is observed all the soils series in the watershed have good permeability.

The percentage of sand, silt of the different soil series in the watershed is taken from report on soils NBSS and LUP, 1995. But while using Wischmeier's equation percentage of sand is not tabulated in the report of (NBSS and LUP, 1995). Percentage of silt, sand is taken in place of percentage of silt, sand plus very fine sand. Therefore particle size distribution curve is not plotted, and K factor is calculated using the available equation.

Weighted average value of K was calculated using the following equation

$$K = \frac{A_1K_1 + A_2K_2 + \dots + A_{11}K_{11}}{A_1 + A_2 + \dots + A_{11}} \quad (1.7)$$

Where,

$A_1, A_2, A_3, \dots A_{11}$ = area of subwatershed 1, 2, 3...11

$K_1, K_2, K_3, \dots K_{11}$ = K-factor for subwatershed 1, 2, 3,...11

The weighted average K is found to be 0.09.

Table 1.1 K – Factor for different soils in the watershed

Soil Texture	Sand (%)	Silt (%)	clay (%)	Structure	Permeability	OM %	K factor
Clay loam	35.74	10.6	53.02	Blocky, Platy or Massive	Slow	0.64	0.12
Habitation mask	0	0	0	-----	-----	0	0
Loam	85.2	4	10	Medium	Moderate	0.8	0.04
Sandy clay loam	65.2	7.29	26.15	Coarse Granular	Slow or Moderate	1.36	0.06
Sandy loam	78.7	4.23	16.28	Medium	Moderate	0.79	0.12
Water body mask	0	0	0	-----	-----	0	0

Table 1.2 K – factor for sub watersheds

Watershed No.	Area (Sq km)	K - factor
1	15.61	0.016
2	15.97	0.054
3	37.07	0.042
4	37.27	0.064
5	21.47	0.045
6	27.17	0.062
7	30.02	0.073
8	13.38	0.068
9	19.36	0.074
10	20.98	0.071
11	43.25	0.08

VIII.SLOPE LENGTH FACTOR (L)

The slope length and gradient are represented in the USLE as L and S respectively. However, they are often evaluated as single topographic factor as LS .

Slope length is defined as the distance from the point of origin of overland flow to the point where either the slope gradient decreases enough that deposition begins or the runoff water enters a well defined channel that may be a part of a drainage network or a constructed channel. However, slope length has been considered as average length of overland flow. The effect of slope length on annual runoff per unit area of cropland may generally be assumed negligible. However, the soil loss per unit area generally increases substantially as slope length increases. The greater accumulation of runoff on the longer slopes increases its detachment and transport capacities.

Slope length factor, can be computed from the following equation

$$L = \left(\frac{l}{22}\right)^m \quad (1.8)$$

Where,

L = slope length factor

l = slope length in m

m = dimensionless exponent

= 0.5 for slopes > 4 %; 0.4 for 4% slope; 0.3 for slopes < 3%

IX.SLOPE STEEPNESS FACTOR (S)

The slope gradient factor is expressed as the ratio of soil loss from a plot of known slope to soil loss from a unit plot under identical conditions. On steep slopes the flow velocity is more, which leads to scouring and cutting of soil. As per Wischmeier and Smith (1978), slope gradient factor is determined by the formula.

$$S = \frac{0.43 + 0.3(\theta) + 0.043(\theta)^2}{6.574} \quad (1.9)$$

Where,

S = slope steepness factor

θ = field slope in percent

Table 1.3 Topographic factors 'LS' for all the watersheds of Harohalli watershed

Watershed No.	Area (Sq.km)	Length (m)	Difference in elevation (m)	Slope (%) $\theta = \tan^{-1}(y/x)$	L factor	S factor	LS Factor
1	15.61	5288	97	1.05	5.18	0.12	0.62
2	15.97	4310	76	1.01	4.87	0.12	0.58
3	37.07	9780	165	0.97	6.23	0.12	0.72
4	37.27	8330	134	0.93	5.94	0.11	0.67
5	21.47	7090	177	1.43	5.66	0.14	0.81
6	27.17	4720	97	1.18	5.01	0.13	0.64
7	30.02	5340	48	0.52	5.19	0.09	0.47
8	13.38	6030	119	1.13	5.39	0.13	0.68
9	19.36	7460	120	0.92	5.74	0.11	0.65
10	20.98	6330	41	0.37	5.47	0.08	0.45
11	43.25	7960	33	0.24	5.86	0.08	0.45

X. CROP MANAGEMENT FACTOR (C)

Factor C in the soil loss equation is the ratio of soil loss from land cropped under specified conditions to the corresponding loss from clean tilled, continuous fallow. This factor measures the combined effect of all the interrelated cover and management variables.

To calculate crop management factor C the whole crop duration is divided into four stages. Therefore the cover and management effects can be considered approximately uniform within each period as;

Period 1: Seeding to one month after seeding.

Period 2: From one to two months after seeding.

Period 3: From two months after seeding to crop harvest.

Period 4: From crop harvest onwards.

As rainfall pattern changes from year to year, average rainfall factor (*R*) for 50 years and percent '*R*' were worked for above and crop stage periods. Ratios of soil loss from cropped plots to corresponding loss from cultivated fallow plots were worked out for these periods as under.

$$C = EI \% \times \text{soil loss} \times 100 \quad (2.0)$$

Thus the total C value for 4 periods will give crop management factor C.

The major crops in the study area include ragi, paddy, Jowar, coffee, tea. However, the C factor is taken from the literature (Dhruva Narayana, 1996) i.e., paddy = 0.28; ragi = 0.60; coffee and tea = 0.52 and so on and the average value 0.48 was taken for the study.

XI. CONSERVATION PRACTICE FACTOR (P)

Conservation practice factor is the ratio of soil loss with a specific supporting practice to the corresponding loss with up and down cultivation. In general, when ever sloping land is to be cultivated and exposed to erosive rain, the protection offered by soil or close growing crops in the system needs to be supported by practices that will slow runoff and thus reduce the amount of soil it carries. The most important support practices are contour cultivation; strip cropping, terrace system and waterways for the disposal of excess rainfall. The values are selected based on the recommendations of Wischmeier and Smith (1958). Since the study area comprised of only field bund conservation P factor was taken as unity. The soil loss estimated from the USLE for all watersheds is shown in Table 1.5.

The average weighted soil loss for the study area is estimated to be 4.23 t/ha/year, which is a nill to slight erosion (ISRO-NNRMS-TR-103 2002). The limits of the soil loss are shown in the Table 1.6.

Table 1.4 Elevation difference for sub watersheds

Watershed No	Area (sq.km)	Perimeter (km)	Length (km)	width (km)	Elevation (m)		Difference in elevation (m)
					Mouth	High Pont	
1	15.61	17.34	5.288	5.17	827	924	97
2	15.97	15.99	4.310	5.62	860	936	76
3	37.07	31.47	9.780	7.95	770	935	165
4	37.27	26.83	8.330	7.82	778	912	134
5	21.47	21.59	7.090	4.56	778	955	177
6	27.17	22.30	4.720	7.54	717	814	97
7	30.02	25.45	5.340	6.76	680	728	48
8	13.38	17.80	6.030	2.79	700	819	119
9	19.36	20.06	7.460	3.16	680	800	120
10	20.98	20.22	6.330	4.46	679	720	41
11	43.25	39.28	7.960	9.15	667	700	33

Table 1.5 Soil loss estimated for sub watersheds

Watershed No.	Area (Km ²)	K-Factor	LS-Factor	Erosion(t/ha/Year)
1	15.61	0.016	0.62	1.19
2	15.97	0.054	0.58	3.76
3	37.07	0.042	0.72	3.63
4	37.27	0.064	0.67	5.15
5	21.47	0.045	0.81	4.38
6	27.17	0.062	0.64	4.77
7	30.02	0.073	0.47	4.12
8	13.38	0.068	0.68	5.55
9	19.36	0.074	0.65	5.77
10	20.98	0.071	0.45	3.84
11	43.25	0.08	0.45	4.32
Total				46.48

Table 1.6 Soil loss limits

Sl.No.	Particulars	Soil loss (t/ha/yr)
1	Nil to slight	Less than 5
2	Slight to moderate	5 to 10
3	Moderate	11 to 25
4	Severe	25 to 50
5	Very severe	Greater than 50

(Source: ISRO-NNRMS-TR-103-2002)

Fig. 1.4 Soil Erosion map of Harohalli Watershed

Table 1.7 Ranges of soil loss in watershed

Soil loss range (t/ha/year)	Area (Sq.km)	% Area
<5	196.94	69.95
>5	84.62	30.05
TOTAL	281.56	100.00

XI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The soil loss for watersheds in the Harohalli watershed was estimated using Revised Universal Soil Loss equation (RUSLE) which comprises of 6 major factors i.e, *RKLSCP*. Rainfall erosivity factor, R was taken directly as 250 from the published Isopleth Map of India (Raghunath et al., 1982), the rainfall erodibility factor (K) was evaluated by using Wischmeier and Smith (1978) equation and the value obtained was found to be 0.09, the slope length and slope steepness was calculated using the Wischmeier and Smith equation (LS) and the value obtained was found to be 0.61. The crop management factor (C) was taken as the average values for various crops grown in watersheds by considering the dominant crop and the average value obtained was 0.48. Since the watershed comprises only bunds around the agricultural lands and no conservation were followed, the conservation practice factor P was taken as unity. The weighted soil erosion for the Harohalli watershed was estimated to be 4.23 t/ha/year which is slight loss (ISRO-NNRMS-TR-103-2002).

From Table 1.5 it can be observed that the soil loss is nil to slight from all the watersheds except in watershed 4, 8 and 9 where the soil loss is slight to moderate and the values of soil loss estimated for the watersheds varies from 1.2 to 5.77 t/ha/year. Fig. 1.4 shows the soil erosion map of watershed. The entire watershed area suffers from severe soil loss (ISRO-NNRMS-TR-103-2002), this may be mainly due to the steep slopes and undulating topography of the watershed. Table 6.6 shows the soil loss ranges in the watershed. About 30.05 % of the area of the watershed is vulnerable to slight to moderate soil erosion which falls under the range of >5 t/ha/year. Similarly about 69.95 % of the area of the watershed is vulnerable to nil to slight soil erosion which falls under the range of <5 t/ha/year. The estimation of soil loss using RUSLE will provide information about the vulnerability of area prone to soil loss and conservation of natural resource within the watershed for sustainable management of soil resource for better crop yield.

Soil loss observed under cropland at all the sub watersheds was varying. Very low soil erosion was observed from watershed, it might be because high management, practice was taken into consideration for computation. Soil loss was found ranging from low to moderate loss in all the classes under forestland but it was of very low soil loss.

The soil loss for watersheds in the Harohalli watershed was estimated to be 4.23 t/ha/year, which is not affected to the entire watershed because of most of the watershed area covered by rock outcrops, habitation mask, water body mask and agriculture plantation. However, conservation practices are not much required to Harohalli watershed.

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